

THE BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FILAMENT WOUND

TUBES UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE

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Introduction

Glass-reinforced plastic pipes are increasingly used in industrial environments where their strength, low weight and corrosion resistance make them competitive with other materials. Problems have been revealed or accentuated which to some extent lessen the advantages of the material and decrease the confidence of the operators.

Pipes may be fabricated with a variety of constructions and resins, and the elastic or short-term behaviour can be deduced from a knowledge of the properties of the constituents and anisotropic behaviour. However, for most load-bearing applications, the short-term properties cannot be used as a basis for design calculations without some knowledge of the critical limits for failure and time-dependent deformation.

Failure is often described as rupture or, in the case of pipes, bursting, but there can be other definitions of failure, such as loss of stiffness. In glass filament wound pipes leakage or weeping of the pressurising fluid can occur in many cases under internal pressures considerably lower than that required for bursting. This is generally related to cracking between glass fibres and the resin, and it has been suggested that one way of improving the weeping characteristics would be to use resins of higher elongation (1).

Several investigations of the effect of resin flexibility or strain-to-failure on the tensile and flexural behaviour of small strips of glass-reinforced composites have been reported (2-5). The general conclusions were that resin flexibility did not significantly affect the ultimate load or the strain at failure of the composite, but the load at which cracking started increased with resin flexibility. A possible reason for the lack of response in composite properties was that the resin was loaded triaxially, which reduced the flexibility (3). It has been reported that weeping in pipes was influenced more by the ultimate strength of the resin rather than its strain at failure (1).

The purpose of the work reported here was to examine the deformation under internal pressure, in both biaxial and uniaxial loading, of glass filament wound pipes with resins of different flexibilities, particularly noting the weeping and bursting strengths.

Material for Test

For the tests, lengths of approximately 1 metre were cut from 3.5 m lengths of glassfibre reinforced pipe. These pipes were produced on a steel mandrel in a filament winding machine using swathes of glass filaments of about 100 mm wide. The pipes had an internal diameter of 100 mm and were produced in two forms: in one, the filaments were wound at helix angles $\pm 54^{\circ} 44'$ to give a total thickness of approximately 2.5 mm; the other had an integral liner of chopped strand mat material with resin, and the outer layers were filament wound as in the first type, using the same resin throughout, the total thickness being 4 mm.

Both forms of pipe were fabricated with three different polyester resin matrices. The pipes designated B1, B2 and B3 were made from resins having nominal elongations to failure of 2, 6-8 and 16-18 per cent respectively. In the results, the subscript L in the designation of the pipes indicates pipes with the integral chopped strand mat liner.

From burn-off tests, the glass content of the filament wound pipes was 55 and, with liner, 20 per cent volume fraction.

Method of Test

To prevent the ends of the pipe sections splitting under hoop loading, or the pipe wall being damaged in a tensile test, small collars were wound on the ends of the pipe using woven glass cloth and epoxy resins. For the biaxial loading, large collars were wound on each end to retain plugs. The length of the collars was 90 mm, and the thickness was approximately 12 mm.

To seal the pipes under internal pressure, steel plugs with O-rings were inserted. During biaxial tests in which the pipe was unrestrained, the plugs were held by split steel flanges bolted around the collars as in Figure 1. To test uniaxially in the hoop direction, the plugs were retained by steel rods bolted to each plug, as shown in Figure 2, and the pipe was free to contract in length. Tensile tests were carried out using a large universal machine with wedge grips.

Strain gauges were fixed to the outside of the pipe, approximately in the middle, to monitor the deformation in both longitudinal and hoop directions in all tests.

For weepage tests, the tubes were internally pressurized until water droplets or a fine spray became visible. To enable the pipes to be burst, rubber liners were introduced.

Results and Discussion

The general form of deformation produced by biaxial loading of a filament wound pipe under internal pressure as revealed by laser holography, is shown in Figure 3. The general impression is of non-uniform strain - a mean value modulated by a cyclic fluctuation. The presence of an integral chopped strand mat liner tended to lessen the strain variation.

Uniaxial Deformation

The form of pressure-strain diagram for test specimens made with the low-elongation and high-elongation resins loaded solely in the hoop direction is shown in Figure 4. After a short region in which the strain in both hoop

Fig. 1 Pipe Assembled for Pressure Testing in Biaxial Mode

Fig. 2 Pipe Assembled for Pressure Testing in Hoop Mode

Fig. 3 Deformation Under Biaxial Load Revealed by Holography

and longitudinal directions are linearly related to the pressure, there is an extensive region of non-linear behaviour in both hoop and longitudinal directions; the longitudinal strain increases very rapidly with pressure, and in some cases the magnitude even exceeds that of the hoop strain in the region of weepage.

Fig. 4 Internal Pressure-strain Curve for Universal Hoop Loading

In the linear region, values of E_H and ν_{HL} can be obtained. The computed values are given in Table 1, together with the values of pressure at the limit of proportionality, weeping, and bursting.

Pipes which had no integral chopped strand mat liner, failed prematurely by bending during test and leakage occurred.

The strains obtained for various points are given in Table 2. The results of the tensile tests are given in Table 3, and a typical stress-strain diagram in Figure 5. In these tests a maximum load was achieved and then, due to failure of resin, the fibres were free to rotate.

The values of E_H in the hoop direction and E_L in the longitudinal direction agree closely with results obtained elsewhere on pipes with 55 per cent glass and the same winding angle (6, 7). The value of ν_{HL} , Poisson's ratio, in the longitudinal direction, produced by load in the hoop direction, again is of the right order, but the corresponding value ν_{LH} in the hoop direction, produced by load in axial direction, is too small. Theoretically

$$\frac{\nu_{LH}}{\nu_{HL}} = \frac{E_L}{E_H},$$

but the results here do not support this.

The flexibility of the resin affected both the limit of proportionality and the weeping pressure. The more flexible the resin, the higher the weeping pressure but the lower the onset of non-linear behaviour. In the tensile test there was little difference in behaviour between the pipes made with resins of high- and low-elongation.

Fig. 5 Stress-strain Curve for Tensile Loading of Pipe

The occurrence of weeping, even in uniaxial hoop loading where from Puck's analysis (8) the stress transverse to the fibre is very low, indicates that cracking must be occurring in the non-linear region. From the large shear strains involved in the deformation, it can be inferred that there is little or no shear transfer by the resin. Ultimate bursting of lined pipes then may be considered in terms of netting analysis. The flexibility of the resin in the pipes had little effect on bursting. The presence of the chopped strand mat liner does affect the values of pressure at the limit of proportionality and weeping, because of some sharing of load between the layers, but the general behaviour is the same as that for pipes without the liner.

Biaxial Loading

The form of the stress/strain curves under biaxial loading, where pressure is applied to the ends of the pipe as well as in the hoop direction, is shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 for pipes made in resins of low- and high-elongation respectively. Broadly, there is a region in which the strain is proportional to the pressure, followed by a region of non-elastic or non-linear behaviour. The flexibility of the resin can influence the onset of non-linear behaviour, and the form of the non-linear part of the strain/pressure curve.

The values of pressures obtained in the tests for limit of elasticity, weeping and bursting are given in Table 3. The associated strains are given in Table 4.

In the linear region, the ratio of longitudinal strain to hoop strain is approximately 1/4. This is in keeping with the expressions

$$\epsilon_H = \frac{\sigma_H}{E_H} - \nu_{LH} \frac{\sigma_L}{E_L} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\epsilon_L = \frac{\sigma_L}{E_L} - \nu_{HL} \frac{\sigma_H}{E_H} \quad (2)$$

using the values of E_L and E_H in Table 1. The value of ν_{LH} used is that in Table 1 but the value of ν_{HL} was taken as $\nu_{LH}(E_L/E_H)$. In this form of biaxial loading of pipes,

$$\sigma_H = \frac{pr}{t} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_L = \frac{pr}{2t}$$

or

$$\sigma_H = 2\sigma_L.$$

Beyond the limit of proportionality, when it is considered cracking occurs or the resin behaves anelastically, the relations given by equations (1) and (2) no longer hold. The erratic behaviour and the variable strain observed, particularly in the case of pipes made from the high-elongation resin, are thought to be due to rotation of filaments with resin shear.

As the resin flexibility is increased, both the weeping pressure and the bursting pressure of simply filament wound pipes increase, but the limit of proportionality decreases slightly. The increase in weeping and bursting pressure is considered to be due to the decrease in cracking propensity of the resin with increased flexibility. The onset of non-elastic shear of the resin decreases with increased flexibility as shown in the limit of proportionality results.

Beyond the limit of proportionality, as pressure is increased, the rate of increase in strain tends to become equal in both the longitudinal and hoop directions. This implies that, as the cracking increases, the resin transmits less and less of the forces between the fibres, and the filaments carry the complete load. In this case, netting analysis, which then can be applied to the situation, predicts that the strains in both longitudinal and hoop directions are equal to the strain in glass filaments. Also, in this condition, the bursting pressure can be related to the strength of the glass filaments. For the condition $\sigma_H/\sigma_A = 2$ and angle of winding = $54^\circ 44'$, netting analysis predicts that the stress parallel to the fibre is given by

$$\sigma_{1,NET} = 1.5\sigma_H$$

which for 55 volume per cent filaments gives a strength of 1.65 GN/m^2 to the filaments.

If it is assumed that netting analysis, in which there is no shear stress along the fibre direction, can also be applied to the uniaxial hoop condition, it can be shown approximately that in this case

$$\sigma_{H,u} = 0.75\sigma_{H,b}.$$

Comparing the bursting pressures of pipes with integral chopped strand mat liners loading in both modes, the ratio of strengths is greater than 0.75, but less than unity. Rotation of filaments during deformation will increase the winding angle and increase the bursting strength.

Fig. 6 Internal Pressure-strain Curve for Low-elongation Resin

Fig. 7 Internal Pressure-strain Curve for High-elongation Resin

In the biaxial loading condition, the presence of a chopped strand mat liner tends to decrease the bursting strength for pipes made from more flexible resins but does not alter significantly the bursting strength of pipes made from the least flexible resin. It is suggested that prior to bursting, the chopped strand mat liner cracks. In B1 pipes the cracking is accompanied by delamination between the liner and the filament wound layers, and the pressure is then supported largely by the filament wound layers. In B2 and B3 pipes, cracking in the chopped strand mat liner is not accompanied by such delamination, and the pipe deforms with cracking in the internal wall. The cracks produce local stress or strain concentrations which produce failure at lower bursting pressures.

If failure is defined as limit of proportionality or weeping the failure envelopes for pipes made from the low-elongation resin are shown in Figure 8. In tension, it is assumed weeping would occur around the maximum stress.

Fig. 8 Failure Envelope

Many failure criteria have been applied to anisotropic materials, but in the tensile quadrant considered, the simplest criterion generally applied is

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{F_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6}\right)^2 = 1.$$

From Puck's analysis (8), σ_H and σ_L can be related to σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 in the elastic region.

At bursting, only the first term need be considered, which, essentially, is the situation of netting analysis. For other failure criteria, such as limit of proportionality or weeping, the term in σ_1 can be neglected, as σ_1/F is much lower than other terms. By testing in a variety of modes, values of F_2 and F_3 can be assigned. These values will depend on the failure criteria under consideration.

In uniaxial loading, the limit of proportionality tends to be less than that obtained in biaxial loading, whereas the reverse is true for the weeping criterion. There does not seem to be a simple criterion for the process of weeping, as it depends on both the strength and the flexibility of the resin.

Also, when values of F_2 and F_6 , obtained from biaxial loading and hoop loading under internal pressure, are applied to the tensile loading condition, the predicted values are considerably larger than the test results. This may

be due to the measuring techniques employed, but it is considered there will be an effect of stress gradients in the wall of the pipes under internal pressure.

Conclusions

The criterion for failure, where failure is described as limit of proportionality or weeping, has been assumed to be of the form

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{F_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_6}{F_6}\right)^2 = 1$$

where F_2 and F_6 are material parameters.

The results of internal pressure testing, when the loading was either biaxial or uniaxial hoop, indicate that F_2 and F_6 depend on the failure mode and are not simply related to the failure. The values do not agree with pure tension results.

Bursting of glass filament wound pipes under biaxial loading can be described in terms of netting analysis, or in terms of the strength of glass fibres.

Thin-walled filament wound pipes without integral liners tended to bend under high internal pressures, causing leakages or premature failure.

The flexibility of the polyester resin used as matrix in the pipes affected their behaviour somewhat at limit of proportionality, weeping and bursting. As the flexibility of the resin is increased, the weeping and bursting pressures also tended to increase.

The presence of an integral liner of chopped strand mat, with the same resin as matrix in filament wound layers, slightly modified the behaviour of the filament wound pipes, increasing the pressure required to cause leakage but not increasing the bursting pressure.

Notation

E_H	Modulus of elasticity in hoop direction
E_L	Modulus of elasticity in longitudinal direction
F_1, F_2, F_6	Material constants
p	Internal pressure
r	Tube radius
ϵ_H	Strain in hoop direction
ϵ_L	Strain in longitudinal direction
ν_{HL}	Poisson's ratio giving strain in longitudinal direction caused by stress in hoop direction
ν_{LH}	Poisson's ratio giving strain in hoop direction caused by stress in longitudinal direction

σ_H	Stress in hoop direction
$\sigma_{H,b}$	Stress in hoop direction in biaxial test
$\sigma_{H,u}$	Stress in hoop direction in uniaxial test
σ_L	Stress in longitudinal direction
σ_1	Stress in direction parallel to fibres
σ_2	Stress in direction perpendicular to fibres
σ_6	Shear stress in direction of fibres
$\sigma_{1,NET}$	Stress in fibre direction by netting analysis

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Table 1. Results of Hoop Loading on Helically Wound Pipe

Test piece	Limit of proportionality	Weeping pressure	Bursting pressure	Modulus	Poisson's ratio
	MN/m ²	MN/m ²	MN/m ²	GN/m ²	
B1	3.0	10.7	14.5*	20.0	0.68
B1 _L	4.0	12.0	23.2	20.0	0.45
B3	2.5	12.1	13.5*	22.0	0.65
B3 _L	3.0	12.0	24.0	17.5	0.57

*Failed by bending

Table 2. Strain Values for Various Pressures in Hoop Loading

Test piece	μ -strain at limit of proportionality		μ -strain at weeping	
	Hoop	Longitudinal	Hoop	Longitudinal
	B1	2750	-2000	20 000
B1 _L	2500	-1200	12 000	-8 500
B3	2600	-1400	20 000	-11 000
B3 _L	2500	-1600	12 000	-10 000

Table 3. Results of Tensile Tests on Helically Wound Pipe

Test piece	Limit of proportionality	Maximum stress	Modulus of elasticity	Poisson's ratio
	MN/m ²	MN/m ²	GN/m ²	
B1	11.0	36.5	11.4	0.3
B1 _L	12.5	41.0	11.9	0.3
B3	12.0	36.2	11.0	0.5
B3 _L	10.0	46.0	9.5	0.35

Table 4. Results of Biaxial Tests on Helically Wound Pipe

Test piece	Limit of proportionality	Weeping pressure	Bursting pressure
	MN/m ²	MN/m ²	MN/m ²
B1	3.9	8.8	27.1
B1 _L	4.8	11.5	27.3
B2	3.8	10.2	30.4
B2 _L	4.3	12.2	25.7
B3	3.3	11.4	28.8
B3 _L	4.2	14.6	26.0

Table 5. Strain Values for Various Pressures in Biaxial Loading

Test piece	μ strain at limit of proportionality		μ -strain at weeping, μ -strain at 138 bar			
	Hoop	Longitudinal	Hoop	Longitudinal	Hoop	Longitudinal
B1	2750	740	5 340	1900	11 000	5700
B1 _L	2330	630	6 500	2700	8 500	3500
B2	2340	550	8 200	2700	10 300	3500
B2 _L	2400	700	8 000	2000	5 500	2700
B3	2500	500	10 500	2000	12 500	2400
B3 _L	2400	275	9 500	630	9 000	620

SESSION 6:
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